

TECHNICAL REPORT ON THE CERIF-CORE MODEL
SUPPORT FOR THE NEW LATTES PLATFORM AND THE PTCRIS ECOSYSTEM
A DATA PERSPECTIVE FOR STANDARDIZATION AND INTEROPERABILITY

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE CERIF-CORE DATA STANDARD

(CERIF, VIVO, and Persistent Identifiers)

**CONTEXT AND ALIGNMENT WITHIN THE RESEARCH METADATA FRAMEWORK AND
ONTOLOGY ALIGNMENT**

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BACKGROUND FOR THE CERIF-CORE STANDARD AND ONGOING LATTES and CIENCIAVITAE PROJECTS

This report briefly describes the work related to the CERIF-Core model and considerations for use by funding agencies such the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development – CNPq (Brazil) and Foundation for Science and Technology – FCT (Portugal).

Working Paper

Introduction

CERIF is considered a comprehensive information model for the metadata domain of scientific research. Its acronym translates to *Common European Research Information Format* (CERIF). This model was designed to facilitate the exchange of data between the different *Current Research Information Systems* (CRIS). The European Union created CERIF, which is currently maintained by the euroCRIS group, a non-profit group whose goals include advancing interoperability and standards for research information. In this context, the CERIF model describes people, organizations, projects, publications, patents, facilities, equipment, services, funding, measurements, indicators, identifiers, and their connections with other entities in the field of scientific research information. The Entity-Relationship Model (ER Model) that forms the basis of the CERIF model can be used to implement it in various databases and can also be defined in XML for data exchange. In addition, CERIF specifies a semantic layer that provides classifications and vocabularies for the research domain. For academics, research managers, policymakers, and funders, CERIF has several uses and advantages.

The CERIF-Core project was initiated by euroCRIS with the aim of modernizing its current structure refactoring of CERIF model. As CERIF is a complete model for storing scientific research data, the refactoring aimed at a more contemporary modeling approaches with modularity and extensibility at its core. The refactoring of CERIF involved the development and construction of a central model (CERIF-Core) that contains the key elements of the CERIF 1.5 reference, decoupling some elements and moving them to different modules. For some use cases or areas with higher levels of specificity (i.e. funding agencies, higher education institutions, among others), such as national and regional particularities, or specificities of scientific processes, infrastructures or methodologies, the central model will act as a basis on which other parts (i.e. modules) can be developed.

For the scientific research information management community, the restructuring of CERIF has many advantages, but it should also bring new challenges. Its goal is to help the community combine and harmonize research data from multiple sources and platforms. To ensure the quality and usefulness of the refactored CERIF model, multiple stakeholders, including academics, research managers, policymakers, funders, developers, and users, will need to collaborate and coordinate their efforts with the refactoring team in order to build extended modules form the new CERIF-Core.

At the moment of the writing of this report, the CERIF data model was published at the euroCRIS site, and the organization informed at their yearly meeting about the ongoing project to refactor the CERIF model. As already mentioned, this proposition addresses shortcomings of the current CERIF model, in order to modernize it and reduce the perceived complexity, allowing the participation of community members in its future development. This new modelling approach brings modularity, modern serialization formats and is a continuing effort.

The CERIF Refactoring team started this work with the objective of making it more customer level extensible. In some situations, this refactored model should help address use cases that focuses on national platforms and other local endeavors. It will also be aimed at adopting standards that are more in accordance with semantic web initiatives, and thus considers using the latest standards compared to the previous version of CERIF. The CERIF refactoring team adopted higher level of abstraction as possible and notations for exchanging information and to some extent use RDF and OWL languages as its representation.

As stated, the CERIF Refactoring Project started in 2021 and had its first phase funded by euroCRIS organization. The development of CERIF-Core kept focused on producing a new standard that could be separated into modules. This meant that the concepts regarding specific funding agencies properties, project structure, and so on should be dealt with in separate models and that each of them could interact with CERIF-Core elements. The CERIF-Core refactored model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - CERIF Core

Source: <https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core/blob/main/diagrams/core.svg>

In research metadata, interoperability refers to the ability of different CRIS systems to exchange and use research metadata. In the case of the CERIF-Core, it defines entities, attributes, datatypes, serialization strategies, guidelines, and relationships in a way that these concepts are consistent with most CRIS systems. CERIF-Core entities allow different CRIS systems to share each other's data without the need for complex translations or conversions. Another relevant quality for CRIS administrators is the fact that the refactored model defines guidelines for extending the CERIF-Core structure, allowing organizations to tailor the model to their specific regional or national metadata needs.

By defining guidelines for extending the CERIF-Core model, organizations can ensure that their specific needs are met while still maintaining interoperability with other systems. Extending the CERIF model to address regional or country wide needs can also help to promote collaboration and innovation. By tailoring the model to their specific requirements, research or funding organizations can create more efficient and effective CRIS systems. This can lead to better insights and decision-making, as well as improved data management and data governance practices for the organization. Additionally, since the CERIF-Core suggests the practice of extensions with its guidelines, euroCRIS can help to promote collaboration and innovation across different regions and domains and thus consider future structures to the CERIF-Core definitions.

In spite of the fact that the CERIF-Core addresses general concept like project and funding, the refactoring initiative also considered the need for addressing other use cases for stakeholder like funding agency, and that gave it a modular architecture and the ability to factor in new products and take advantage of subclassing practices as shown in Figure 2, that depicts the relationship between Agent and Person, Group and Organizational Unit.

Figure 2 - Agent Module

Source: <https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core/blob/main/diagrams/agent.svg>

As shown in Figure 2, the Agent entity has an abstract level definition and is defined as anything that has the ability to perform activities. The proposed CERIF-Core's Agent Entity is a high-level specification or abstraction intended to be used for a data model. It is one of the entities included in the CERIF-Core model and expected to aid in the development of an information model for the field of scientific research metadata. Researchers, research groups, funding organizations and other entities can be derived by (i.e., is-a relationship or inheritance) the Agent Entity. This entities' attribute, include, contact details, and function in research projects, are described using the term "Agent entity." Additionally, it offers a means to connect these entities with other CERIF model elements including projects, publications, and facilities.

Figure 3 – Activity Model
<https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core/blob/main/diagrams/activity.svg>

Figure 4 - Application Module
<https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core/blob/main/diagrams/application.svg>

The proposed CERIF-Core's Activity Entity is a high-level specification or abstraction intended to be used for a data model. It is one of the entities included in the CERIF-Core model and expected to aid in the development of an information model for the field of scientific research metadata. Researchers, research groups, funding organizations and other entities can be related to Activities by (i.e., is-a relationship or inheritance) the Activity Entity. These entities' attributes include displayAffiliation_Statement, displayPersonName, address, contacts. Additionally, it offers a means to connect these entities with other CERIF model elements including projects, publications, and facilities.

By doing so, it provides a comprehensive information model for the domain of scientific research that can be used to support the interchange of research information between and with CRISs¹².

Figure 5 - Contribution Statement Module

<https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core/blob/main/diagrams/contributionToDocument.svg>

Figure 6 – Membership Entity

<https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core/blob/main/diagrams/membership.svg>

Aligning and identity gaps from CERIF-Core standard (CERIF-R) to the CIENCIAVITAE and LATTES CERIF Model

The purpose of conceptually aligning entities with euroCRIS (CERIF-Core) and other funding organizations can provide them with a number of advantages. To begin, it can help to rationalize the process of managing research information by facilitating the establishment and interoperability of Research Information Systems. Persons, organizations, projects, publications, patents, data, facilities, equipment, services, funding, measurement, indicators, identifiers, and their interactions are all described in CERIF. This enables the development of scalable, interoperable, and high-quality information systems that can be used to structure, store, manage, share, access, disseminate, or evaluate the information contained inside them.

Enhancing the discoverability of research results is another reason for aligning entities from CERIF-CORE with CNPq (e.g. Lattes, GRPESQ, PICC etc.), and FCT (CIENCIAVITAE, SciProj, RCAAAP, etc.). Researchers once informed they metadata to one of these funding agencies, can make sure that their research outputs are discoverable by other researchers and organizations by aligning entities from CERIF-CORE to other systems. Their research results may become more visible as a result, which may eventually result in more citations and a bigger effect. Additionally, researchers can guarantee that their research outputs are adequately defined and classified by aligning entities from CERIF-CORE to other systems, which can assist ensure that they are used appropriately by other researchers and organizations.

Conceptual Entity Alignment - euroCRIS (CERIF-Core), CNPq (Lattes, PICC, GRPESQ, BI) , FCT (CIENCIAVITAE, SciProj, RCAAAP)			CNPq - National Council for Scientific and Technological Development			FCT - Fundação for Science and Technology		
CERIF Refactored - CORE			Lattes, PICC, GRPESQ and BI			CIENCIAVITAE, SciProj, RCAAAP		
Entities	Type	Link to the code repository	Entities	Type	Link to the code repository	Entities	Type	Link to the code repository
Activity	CERIF-Core	https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core/blob/main/diagrams/activity.svg	EN_AREA_CONHEC	Lattes-CV		EN_AJUDA_CONTEXTUAL	CienciaVITAE	
Affiliation_Statement	CERIF-Core		EN_COAUTOR	Lattes-CV		EN_AREA_CONHEC	CienciaVITAE	
Agent	CERIF-Core	https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core/blob/main/diagrams/agent.svg	EN_DEFINICAO	Lattes-CV		EN_CDAUTOR	CienciaVITAE	
Agent_Identifier	CERIF-Core		EN_FORMACAO	Lattes-CV		EN_DEFINICAO	CienciaVITAE	
Application	CERIF-Core	https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core/blob/main/diagrams/application.png	EN_IDOMA	Lattes-CV		EN_FORMACAO	CienciaVITAE	
Application_Review	CERIF-Core		EN_LOG	Lattes-CV		EN_IDOMA	CienciaVITAE	
Authorship	CERIF-Core		EN_LOG_AP	Lattes-CV		EN_LOG	CienciaVITAE	
Call_for_Applications	CERIF-Core		EN_LOG_GERA_INCONS	Lattes-CV		EN_LOG_AP	CienciaVITAE	
Call_for_Funding_Applications	CERIF-Core		EN_LOG_GERA_PDF	Lattes-CV		EN_LOG_GERA_INCONS	CienciaVITAE	
Condition	CERIF-Core		EN_LOG_NOTIFICACAO	Lattes-CV		EN_LOG_GERA_PDF	CienciaVITAE	
Contribution	CERIF-Core		EN_MOEDA	Lattes-CV		EN_LOG_NOTIFICACAO	CienciaVITAE	
Contribution_Statement	CERIF-Core		EN_ORCID_ACCESS_TOKEN	Lattes-CV		EN_MOEDA	CienciaVITAE	
Contribution_to_Document	CERIF-Core	https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core/blob/main/diagrams/contribution_to_document.svg	EN_PMS	Lattes-CV		EN_ORCID_ACCESS_TOKEN	CienciaVITAE	
Contribution_to_Evaluation_Outcome	CERIF-Core		EN_PLV_CHANGE	Lattes-CV		EN_ORCID_SYNC_ERROR_LOG	CienciaVITAE	
Contribution_to_Event	CERIF-Core		EN_POST_IT	Lattes-CV		EN_PMS	CienciaVITAE	
Contribution_to_Infrastructure	CERIF-Core		EN_PREMIAÇÃO	Lattes-CV		EN_PLV_CHANGE	CienciaVITAE	
Contribution_to_Project	CERIF-Core		EN_PRODUCAO	Lattes-CV		EN_POST_IT	CienciaVITAE	
Decision	CERIF-Core		EN_PRODUTOS	Lattes-CV		EN_PREMIAÇÃO	CienciaVITAE	
Dissemination	CERIF-Core		EN_RECUSADO_HUMANAO	Lattes-CV		EN_PRODUCAO	CienciaVITAE	
Evaluation	CERIF-Core		EN_REPOSITARIO	Lattes-CV		EN_PRODUTOS	CienciaVITAE	
Employment	CERIF-Core		EN_REPOSITARIO_DOMINIO_EMAIL	Lattes-CV		EN_RECUSADO_HUMANAO	CienciaVITAE	
Evaluation_Outcome	CERIF-Core		EN_REPOSITARIO_LOG	Lattes-CV		EN_REPOSITARIO	CienciaVITAE	
Event	CERIF-Core		EN_REPOSITARIO_WORKFLOW	Lattes-CV		EN_REPOSITARIO_DOMINIO_EMAIL	CienciaVITAE	
Expertise_and_Skills	CERIF-Core		EN_BIO_EMAIL	Lattes-CV		EN_REPOSITARIO_LOG	CienciaVITAE	

Figure 7 - Application Module

By making it possible to build up and interact with other research information systems, CERIF also offers a formal architecture to help the management of research information. It has been developed over the course of two significant phases, from 1987 to 1990 and from 1997 to 1999. CERIF is regarded as a benchmark for research information management and is an EU recommendation to Member States. It has been created to be versatile and flexible to various situations and needs. Research information can be managed more effectively and efficiently by cooperating with CERIF-Core and other regional organizations for funding agencies.

Conceptual Entity Alignment - euroCRIS (CERIF-Core), CNPq (Lattes, PIIIC, GRPESQ, DI) , FCT (CIENCIAVITAE, SciProj, RCAAAP)

Contribution_to_Project -> EN_PROJETO

euroCRIS			CNPq - National Council for Scientific and Technological Development			FCT - Foundation for Science and Technology		
CERIF Refactored - CORE			Lattes, PIIIC, GRPESQ and DI			CIENCIAVITAE, SciProj, RCAAAP		
Attributes	Type	Link to Hierarchy or composition	Attributes	Type	Link to the code repository	Attributes	Type	
Agent_Identifier			NRO_ID_CNPQ	NUMBER		NRO_ID_CNPQ	NUMBER	
displayAffiliation_Statement	String	Activity	SEQ_PROJETO	NUMBER		SEQ_PROJETO	NUMBER	
displayPersonName	String	Activity	SQL_PAS	VARCHAR2(3 CHAR)		SQL_PAS	VARCHAR2(3 CHAR)	
address	Postal_Address	Activity	COD_IDIOMA	VARCHAR2(7 CHAR)		COD_IDIOMA	VARCHAR2(7 CHAR)	
contacts	List URI	Activity	COD_TIPO_PROJETO	VARCHAR2(4 CHAR)		COD_TIPO_PROJETO	VARCHAR2(4 CHAR)	
fontSize	Data_Range	Agent	TXT_TITULO	VARCHAR2(350 BYTE)		TXT_TITULO	VARCHAR2(350 BYTE)	
DOI	DOI	Activity (Document composition)	TXT_DESCRICA	VARCHAR2(4000 BYTE)		TXT_DESCRICA	VARCHAR2(4000 BYTE)	
title	Multi lingual_String	Activity (Document composition)	TPO_STATUS_FINANCIAMENTO	VARCHAR2(1 CHAR)		TPO_STATUS_FINANCIAMENTO	VARCHAR2(1 CHAR)	
publicationDate	Date	Activity (Document composition)	TPO_NATUREZA_FINANCIAMENTO	VARCHAR2(1 CHAR)		TPO_NATUREZA_FINANCIAMENTO	VARCHAR2(1 CHAR)	
project	Project	Resource	TXT_PROGRAMA	VARCHAR2(255 CHAR)		TXT_PROGRAMA	VARCHAR2(255 CHAR)	
amount_of_time_in_person_hours	Decimal		NUM_VALOR	VARCHAR2(100 CHAR)		NUM_VALOR	VARCHAR2(100 CHAR)	
amount	Monetary Amount		TPO_MODAL	VARCHAR2(3 CHAR)		TPO_MODAL	VARCHAR2(3 CHAR)	
List of Activity and Agent	VERIFY	How to fill a Agent and Activity of Project	NUM_VALOR_PESSOA	NUMBER		NUM_VALOR_PESSOA	NUMBER	
			TPO_COMPETITIVO	VARCHAR2(1 CHAR)		TPO_COMPETITIVO	VARCHAR2(1 CHAR)	
			TPO_EXTENSIVEL	VARCHAR2(1 CHAR)		TPO_EXTENSIVEL	VARCHAR2(1 CHAR)	
			TPO_BOLSA_CONTRATO	VARCHAR2(10 CHAR)		TPO_BOLSA_CONTRATO	VARCHAR2(10 CHAR)	
			NUM_PERCENTAGEM_ALOCADO	NUMBER		NUM_PERCENTAGEM_ALOCADO	NUMBER	
			TPO_PERFIL_INVESTIGADOR	VARCHAR2(3 CHAR)		TPO_PERFIL_INVESTIGADOR	VARCHAR2(3 CHAR)	
						TXT_OBSERVACAO	VARCHAR2(4000 CHAR)	
						NUM_PRIVACIDADE	VARCHAR2(20 CHAR)	
						DTA_Ult_ATUALIZ	DATE	
						DTA_INI_PROJETO	VARCHAR2(10 CHAR)	
						DTA_FIM_PROJETO	VARCHAR2(10 CHAR)	
						NUM_ANO_PREMIO	VARCHAR2(4 CHAR)	
						DTA_FIM_PART_PROJETO	VARCHAR2(10 CHAR)	
						DTA_INI_PART_PROJETO	VARCHAR2(10 CHAR)	

Conceptual Entity Alignment - euroCRIS (CERIF-Core), CNPq (Lattes, PIIIC, GRPESQ, DI) , FCT (CIENCIAVITAE, SciProj, RCAAAP)

euroCRIS			CNPq - National Council for Scientific and Technological Development					
CERIF Base Entities in Context			CERIF Refactored - CORE			Lattes, PIIIC, GRPESQ and DI		
Entities	Type	Entities	Type	Link to the code repository	Entities	Type	Link to the code repository	
cOrigUnit	Base Entities	Activity	CERIF-Core	https://github.com/eur01/151301/commit/5a0e0b0400000000000000000000000000000000	"fed","Yedid"	Federated Identifier		
cOrigUnit_OrgUnit	Base Entities	Affiliation_Statement	CERIF-Core		"fed","Yedid_Class"	Federated Identifier		
cPRes	Base Entities	Agent	CERIF-Core	https://github.com/eur01/151301/commit/5a0e0b0400000000000000000000000000000000	"fed","Yedid_Sex"	Federated Identifier		
cPRes_Pers	Base Entities	Agent_Identifier	CERIF-Core		"fed","Fund"	Funding		
cProj	Base Entities	Application	CERIF-Core	https://github.com/eur01/151301/commit/5a0e0b0400000000000000000000000000000000	"fed","Fund_Fund"	Funding		
cProj_Proj	Base Entities	Applications_Review	CERIF-Core		"fed","Fund_Indic"	Funding		
cOrigUnitKeyw	Base Entities	Authorship	CERIF-Core		"fed","Fund_Mean"	Funding		
cOrigUnitName	Base Entities	Call for Applications	CERIF-Core		"fed","FundPlan"	Funding		
cOrigUnitResAct	Base Entities	Call for Funding Applications	CERIF-Core		"fed","FundDeser"	Funding		
cPersKeyw	Base Entities	Condition	CERIF-Core		"fed","FundKeyw"	Funding		
cPersName	Base Entities	Contribution	CERIF-Core		"fed","FundName"	Funding		
cPersName_Pers	Base Entities	Contribution_Statement	CERIF-Core		"lang"			
cPersResAct	Base Entities	Contribution to Document	CERIF-Core	https://github.com/eur01/151301/commit/5a0e0b0400000000000000000000000000000000	"lang"			
cProjAbstr	Base Entities	Contribution to Evaluation Outcome	CERIF-Core		"lang_Class"			
cProjKeyw	Base Entities	Contribution to Event	CERIF-Core		"langName"			
cProjTime	Base Entities	Contribution to Infrastructure	CERIF-Core		"Mean"			
cPRes_OrgUnit	Base Entities	Contribution to Project	CERIF-Core		"org","OrgUnit"	Organizational Unit		
cProj_OrgUnit	Base Entities	Decision	CERIF-Core		"org","OrgUnit_Class"	Organizational Unit		
cProj_Pers	Base Entities	Document	CERIF-Core		"org","OrgUnit_Dc"	Organizational Unit		
cOrigUnit_OrgUnitName	Base Entities	Education	CERIF-Core		"org","OrgUnit_Eaddr"	Organizational Unit		
cOrigUnit_OrgUnitKeyw	Base Entities	Employment	CERIF-Core		"org","OrgUnit_Equip"	Organizational Unit		
cOrigUnit_OrgUnitResAct	Base Entities	Evaluation_Outcome	CERIF-Core		"org","OrgUnit_Event"	Organizational Unit		
cOrigUnit_OrgUnit_OrgUnit3	Base Entities	Event	CERIF-Core		"org","OrgUnit_ExpSkills"	Organizational Unit		

This is a strong representation, since it addresses various issues regarding managing a data fabric that is responsible for data extraction, metadata management, data rules and policies maintenance, data quality procedures, data profiling procedures, building knowledge graphs and data transformation procedures in order to provide data products for the organization.

Figure 8 - Proposed translation from the CERIF-Core Class Diagram to a ER Diagram

It is important to point out that UML and OWL version 2 both have address a concept of class as a description for a set of objects that have the same structure, behavior, and relationships, and this could have motivated the use of a UML diagram for this visual representation of the CERIF-Core standard representation. In the UML class diagram notation, a class can have attributes that determine the structure and the operation, that determine the behavior of the instance of the class. A class in OWL is an empty set or has multiple instances and do not define operations on those instances. The types of relationships are similar between the UML and OWL notations, but in respect to the behavior, will result in implications that have very distinct differences. In UML, the object-oriented paradigm will determine that relationships like inheritance and aggregation and composition can provoke in subclasses or related classes a consequence to add methods or behave in a polymorphic characteristic in specific methods.

During the project, the steps taken to elaborate an ER diagram from the CERIF-Core class diagram included identifying classes and entities and adapting them so that they represent data persistency concerns. In these steps, all selected classes became entities in the ER diagram and most of the attributes were defined for corresponding to the class in the UML diagram. As examples of the steps done to conduct the translation are as follows:

First step: reviewing relationships and defined them in the ER diagram. Identify relationships between entities in the CERIF-Core class diagram and how they can map to the ER diagram. In the ERD, the represented relationships focus on connecting the entity tables and concern more of representing the cardinality between data instances. The cardinality notation defines the nature of the relationships (e.g., one-to-one, one-to-many, many-to-many).

Second step: normalizing for the data structure and the translation from object-oriented relationship. As an ER representation, there is a need to normalize the data to minimize redundancy and improve data integrity. Ensure that data is organized into tables to adhere to the principles of

normalization. For this reason, the attributes structured changed from the UML diagram to the ER diagram, mainly adding the key relationships.

Third step: incorporating constraints and added attributes to conform with the data integrity premises. Add constraints such as primary keys, foreign keys, and unique constraints to enforce data integrity, since in the UML class diagram this type of representation is not needed, and object identifiers are resolved in memory allocation within the runtime environment.

Fourth step: reviewing and refining the translated structure. The work reviewed the ER diagram to verify that it reflected the classes in the translated data model.

In addition to the steps in translating the CERIF-Core UML diagram to an ER diagram, some rules helped. Some of the rules to conduct the translation are as follows:

For each UML class in the CERIF-Core that is transformed into class ER diagram, verify how the DisjointClasses are represented³. The second rule in the transformation process looks to the attributes of the class in the CERIF-Core which has a primitive data type and verify the range and the corresponding data type, and domain and range.

Figure 9 - Diagram Crow's Foot Notation from part of the CERIF-Core UML Diagram

Identifying potential limitations in the CERIF-Core proposed model

The ability to produce an open and generic data interoperability model that could be multilingual and capable of addressing a variety of multinational data structures, formats, and terminologies is the primary goal of common models like the CERIF-Core proposed standard. With the use of the common ontological model like the CERIF-Core, technical staff can write code and develop mapped dataset and then run it on several datasets that can tackle regional and local business requirements. While the

³ Zaremba, I., & Kodors, S. (2013). Automatic transformation of UML geospatial profile to OWL ontologies. Virtual multidisciplinary conference QUAESTI.

some are involved in the implementation, the standardization staff are required be acquainted with the distinctiveness of numerous of national and regional datasets. Defining standards and ontological resources for the CERIF-Core model makes it possible for a community to work together to design and create pipelines that foster the interoperability using the CERIF-Core as a *lingua franca*. This brings a challenge to the team designing the CERIF-Core ontological structure, as it adds a level of abstraction and ontological commitments that aren't needed when the structure addresses only local concerns.

This part of the project focused on evaluating the CERIF-Core ontology and understanding the proposed classes, relationships, attributes that were in the UML class diagram. During the review process and the subsequent translation to the ER model, there were some issues that related to the interpretation of the UML notation and its consequences for the abstractions and concepts used by the CERIF-Core standard. The process included the review process.... There were meetings in 2023 and 2024 during this review process and during this period, we worked on the several scenarios of recommendations that were discussed in various circumstances of use.

Scenario 1: Recommendation regarding cardinality in Document and Activity relationship.

In a UML class diagram, relationships are represented by as lines connecting two or more classes and added symbols at the end of each line that can reflect the cardinality (i.e. number of instances that one class commits to that relationship). After reviewing the CERIF-Core proposed diagram, there were some issues with the relationship annotation and cardinality. One example shown is the Figure below was the relationship between Document and Activity classes. Based on the notation in the proposed diagram, implementing this relationship could lead to having “no instances”, between a Document and an Activity, that could also impact the relationship with the class Contribution_to_Document, as it shows an association that implies a cardinality 1:1 . Since Contribution_to_Document is a subclass of Contribution, the cardinality implies that there should be at least on instance of an Activity, therefore this can be eventually an issue of number of instances for these relationships.

Scenario 2: Recommendation regarding identifiers for agents

Persistent identifiers are a fundamental part of information in research and are an ongoing discussion in the research metadata community. In scenario 2, one relationship between class Agent and Agent_identifier as shown in the figure below can create an issue since it allows that an instance of Agent does not need an instance associated with a Agent_identifier. The recommendation is that the class Agent have at least one Agent_identifier, since it could be considered an instance of a Local Identifier. The recommendation is to set the cardinality to be 1..* - 1 (at least 1 to 1 or 1 to many).

Scenario 3: Recommendation regarding cardinality between Involvement and Affiliation Statement

In this situation the UML diagram allows that an instance of the class Involvement does not have to have an Affiliation_Statement. The Affiliation_Statement has the structure to represent the Agent's connection to a Research Institution and since it could be a list of these organizations, having an instance of Affiliation_Statement can help reduce ambiguity and enhance correctness in the data for the Involvement. This is the reason that the recommendation that the class Agent_identifier considers a Local Identifier; this cardinality should be 1..* - 1 (at least 1 to 1 or 1 to many)

Scenario 4: Recommendation regarding the composition of Contribution and Contribution Statement

In this situation the UML diagram defines a relationship between the class Contribution and Contribution_Statement that is of type “composition”, and on the Contribution_Statement side, the cardinality is 0..*. This can create a situation where for a new Instance of Contribution, one of its attributes could be a null value to the instance of a Contribution_Statement, producing a potential problem, as composition relationships suggest that the parts should be addresses the instance of Contribution created.

Scenario 5: Recommendation regarding the relationship between Contribution and Contribution to Project and Contribution to Event

In this situation the UML diagram defines a relationship between the class Contribution and Contribution to Project and Contribution to Event as a simple association. The issues pointed out are: can one have more contributions to one project or event and can the relationship be of composition, between Contribution and Contribution to Project and Contribution to Event since there is no reason for an instance of these inherited classes from Contribution without instances of Project or Event.

Scenario 6: Recommendation regarding the datatype of an attribute from the class Affiliation Statement

In this situation the UML diagram defines a datatype of an attribute from the class Affiliation_Statement named Position, that has a title and a code. In this situation, the cardinality of this attribute is 0..1 to 0, and the recommendation is that it should be at least 1, since there is a need of data from the position to understand the person's role in the organization.

The second recommendation is that the relationship between Affiliation_Statement and the class Activity be at least with a cardinality of one, since there is a need to have data on what the activity was and its date range.

Scenario 7: Recommendation regarding cardinality and Contribution Statement and its Resources

In this situation the UML diagram defines a relationship between the Contribution_Statement class and the Resource_Usage_Statement, and both have a relationship of association with the class Resource. These same classes have a relationship between each other of aggregation making these attributes have the same name and different cardinalities. As a recommendation, have a named relationship that can distinguish these attributes in a sense that it will be understood as a supplied resource and a consumed resource and the cardinality of at least 1.

Ontology Alignment base on Competency Questions

Using natural language questions provide a means to address the concerns from stakeholders and are in the context of organizational knowledge. They help verify the knowledge represented in an ontology and are called competency questions (CQ). The CQs are a component of many ontology engineering approaches and engineers build corresponding SPARQL-OWL queries to analyze their results to confirm if the ontology structure can respond adequately to each stated competency question. In this project, the natural language text was analyzed linguistically, specifically focusing on identifying classes within the research and metadata structure provided by Ontologies from VIVO and other research data standards. The project also performed a semantic analysis to look for patterns and find related taxonomies or other references used by other research data standards groups.

Q#	Text of associated/developed projects with specific details.	Ont. class	Project	Q#	Text of associated/developed projects with specific details.	Ont. class	Project
Q048	Obtain a list of projects that received funding based on a research topic.	The user wants to know for a given Project, what research field (interdisciplinary) focus it has.	Project	Q049	Obtain a list of projects that are related to a Knowledge Area .	The user wants to know for a given Project, what interdisciplinary research field focus it has.	Project
Q049	Obtain a list of projects that are related to a Knowledge Area .	The user wants to know for a given Project, what subject classification it has.	Project	Q050	Obtain a list of projects that are related to a Knowledge Area .	The user wants to know for a given Project, what subject classification it has.	Project
Q050	Obtain a list of Organizations (units or research centers) that have	The user wants to know for a given Project, what subject classification it has.	Project	Q051	Obtain a list of Organizations (units or research centers) that have	The user wants to know for a given Project, what subject classification it has.	Project

This evaluation focused on existing gaps based on the list of competency questions from the VIVO ontology, the HERCULES ontology, the KDSF ontology, CERIF-Core ontology, Lattes and CIENCIAVITAE ontologies. The study first focused at existing references that addressed the Project class in more detailed manner and suggest scenarios to align with it.

Formulário para catalogar as ontologias contemporâneas de Currículos Acadêmicos					
Ontologia: Ministério da Educação					
Informação / Característica / Descrição / Contexto de uso da ontologia	Atividades das Ontologias	VIVO	LATTES (Informal)	CIENCIAVITAE	CIERP
Informação / Característica / Descrição / Contexto de uso da ontologia	Atividades das Ontologias	VIVO	LATTES (Informal)	CIENCIAVITAE	CIERP
Atividade de uso da ontologia	Atividades das Ontologias	VIVO	LATTES (Informal)	CIENCIAVITAE	CIERP
Informação / Característica / Descrição / Contexto de uso da ontologia	Atividades das Ontologias	VIVO	LATTES (Informal)	CIENCIAVITAE	CIERP
Atividade de uso da ontologia	Atividades das Ontologias	VIVO	LATTES (Informal)	CIENCIAVITAE	CIERP

